

Ellipticity Distribution Bug in cosmoDC2 and SkySim5000_v1.1.1

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We describe the bug in the ellipticity values and related quantities that are present in the cosmoDC2 catalogs and SkySim5000_v1.1.1 and discuss how the error should be corrected. We show distributions of the uncorrected and corrected values. The bug resulted in the distribution of ellipticities being skewed to lower values, i.e., galaxies are rounder than they should have been. This bug affects the intrinsic (pre-lensing) galaxy ellipticities; the lensing shape distortions were unaffected in the catalog, and are added to the too-round intrinsic shapes. These ellipticities were used as the inputs for the DC2 image simulations, therefore the DC2 image simulations and resulting object catalogs are affected.

Description of the Bug

We have confirmed that there is a bug in the galaxy intrinsic ellipticity distributions in the cosmoDC2 catalog.

In the catalog production code, an empirical model is used to generate ellipticity distributions for the disk and bulge components of each galaxy to match the observed distributions for COSMOS data. The COSMOS data are also used in the validation test and are described by Johnson B distributions with separate parameter values for disk and bulge ellipticities. The parameters are also dependent on the rest-frame r-band magnitudes for each galaxy component. Note that the COSMOS data uses the “distortion” definition of ellipticity i.e. $e_d = (1-q^2)/(1+q^2)$, where q denotes the axis ratio. The production code correctly generated the Johnson B distributions for the disk and bulge distortion ellipticities. However, there was an error in computing the axis ratio from the ellipticity. Specifically, the bug was caused by the following error in the code to compute the axis ratios from the generated ellipticity distributions:

$$q_{\text{bad}} = \sqrt{((1 - e_d^2)/(1 + e_d^2))}.$$

The correct relationship should have been

$$q = \sqrt{(1 - e_d)/(1 + e_d)}.$$

This error affects all of the quantities in the catalog related to ellipticities including the native quantities in the ‘morphology’ group, except for the ‘position_angle’, and the ellipticity* and

size*minor* quantities that are obtained from the GRCatalogs reader (i.e., the so-called 'schema' quantities). Note that the definition of ellipticity used in the schema is the shear definition which implies an axis ratio given by:

$$q = (1 - e_s)/(1 + e_s),$$

where e_s denotes the shear ellipticity.

The error was not caught by the DESCQA test because there was a compensating bug in the definition of the distortion ellipticity in the DESCQA test so that the catalog distributions agreed with the COSMOS data.

Verification of the Error

We performed several code checks to verify the error and validate the code to correct it. We modified the GRCatalog reader to back out the incorrect values and recompute the correct values for the ellipticity* quantities supplied by the reader. We also compared them with the values obtained from the Johnson B distributions of the empirical model. The results are shown below.

Here we show distributions for disk and bulge ellipticities for selected galaxies calculated in various ways, along with the distributions for the total ellipticity (cyan), which are the luminosity weighted sums of the disk and bulge ellipticities. The galaxy selections approximately match the selections in the COSMOS data. The disk and bulge ellipticity distributions are calculated from: (1) the corrected axis ratios obtained from the GCR reader (red), (2) reverse engineered from incorrect axis ratios available as native quantities in the catalog (blue), (3) converted from corrected shear ellipticity values from the GCR reader (green), and (4) generated from the model Johnson B distributions (magenta) using the

model parameters. Note that the distributions are offset by .01 so you can see the different lines. All of these distributions agree with each other, as expected. Furthermore we see that the distribution for the total ellipticity lies between the disk and bulge distributions, also as expected.

We further validate the distributions by checking how the bulge-to-total (B/T) cuts that are applied to the catalog data in the validation test approximate the disk and bulge ellipticity distributions.

Here we show the total ellipticity distributions with different B/T cuts applied (blue, green, magenta) and compare them with the component ellipticity distribution (red) for the disk and bulge components. We see that the distribution with $0 < B/T < 0.2$ almost reproduces the disk ellipticity distribution while the distribution with $0.7 < B/T < 1.0$ is close to that of the bulge ellipticity. This plot verifies that the B/T cut approximately reproduces the morphology selections that we are trying to match in the validation test.

The Corrected and Uncorrected Distributions

Here we show a comparison of the corrected (red) and uncorrected (blue) distributions for the distortion ellipticity. We see that the uncorrected distributions are skewed towards low values of the ellipticity. That is, the galaxies are too round, on average. This has implications for the DC2 image simulations, blending and any other analysis that uses galaxy shape measurements.

The DESCQA Validation Test

As a final check, we have used the corrected ellipticity values from the catalog reader to rerun the corrected DESCQA validation test.

The result of the test is shown above and is identical to the earlier result except that the definition of e (x-axis) is now corrected.

Potential Mitigation Strategies

Here we list some options for correcting this problem:

- Produce new versions of the catalogs (eg. cosmoDC2_v1.1.5 and SkySim5000_v1.2.0) that have corrected quantities. This has the benefit of making it clear that the previous version has been superseded. In this case, the GCR reader would be unchanged, except possibly to issue a warning that the ellipticity quantities are incorrectly distributed for cosmoDC2_v1.1.4 and SkySim5000_v1.1.1. This warning needs to be carefully worded to ensure that people understand the context of the statement. The new version of the cosmoDC2 catalog should also be made available on the public website.

- Use the GRCatalogs reader to correct the incorrect schema quantities. This does not correct the native quantities, but it is possible to correct these as well by overwriting the native quantities. (The overwritten quantities have the same names as the original quantities, but are transformed into derived quantities). Correcting the reader has implications for analyses/image simulations that have used cosmoDC2_v1.1.4 in the past, so this solution is not preferred for that reason. Since the image simulations and the resulting object catalogs are based on the incorrect inputs, we need to preserve cosmoDC2_v1.1.4 so that it can be used as truth information for the image simulations.. Another argument against this option is that correcting the reader does not address users who bypass the reader and read the catalog directly in hdf5 or parquet format.
- This note needs to be widely disseminated within the collaboration and to be made publicly available to ensure that all users are made aware of the issue. In particular, it should be available from the public website from which cosmoDC2_v1.1.4 can be downloaded.
- Other suggestions are open for discussion.

Impact on DC2 Image Simulations

These incorrect ellipticity distributions were used as inputs for the galaxy shapes in the DC2 image simulations. Therefore, we expect that the distribution of intrinsic shapes of galaxies in the simulated images and in the object catalogs are rounder than they should be. There is agreement between the catalog and truth information but the observed ratios will also be affected by the PSF.